

Beyond age gates: a brief behavioral validity screen as a risk-tiering layer for social AI companions

Pawel Szczesny¹

1 - Impersonato PSA, ul.Pulawska 77/U5, Warsaw Poland

pawel.szczesny@impersonato.com

Abstract — Current safety protocols for social AI companions rely on binary age thresholds (e.g., "18+") or self-reported declarations of maturity. However, chronological age poorly predicts psychosocial capacity to navigate high-intimacy AI systems, and self-report is easily gamed by users seeking unrestricted access. Adolescence is characterized by significant heterogeneity in social cognition and regulatory capacity; a 16-year-old and an 18-year-old may possess comparable capabilities regarding impulse control, rejection tolerance, and boundary reasoning. This paper argues that high-intimacy AI affordances require a safety layer beyond age verification: a brief, validity-informed behavioral screening battery. This screening tiers access to high-risk features (e.g., erotic roleplay, exclusivity cues) based on vulnerability-relevant metrics, such as inhibitory control or mentalization. Performance validity testing (PVT) informed checks help detect invalid responding/gaming, while task performance provides probabilistic vulnerability signals. An operational framework for risk-tiering is presented, alongside evaluation metrics, privacy safeguards to prevent discriminatory deployment and example implementation as a Chrome browser extension.

Keywords: AI companions, adolescents, attachment, parasocial relationships, age assurance, performance validity, risk tiering

Introduction

AI companions are used as relational systems—as agents users bond with, disclose to, and sometimes treat as friends or partners. Empirical work has modeled engagement with companion platforms as relationship development, characterized by bonding and intimacy expectations (Pentina et al. 2023).

For adolescents, the stakes are unique. “Relationship competence” is typically learned through repeated exposure to real-world contingencies: reciprocity, boundaries, misattunement, repair, and rejection tolerance. Public health frameworks frame adolescence as extending roughly from 10 to 24 (Sawyer et al. 2018), but newer structural topology analyses suggest even wider, 9 to 32, adolescence phase (Mousley et al. 2025). This does not redefine adolescence as a clinical or sociological category, but it is consistent with the broader point that maturational trajectories relevant to social cognition and self-regulation extend well beyond a single legal age boundary.

Neurodevelopmental literature likewise emphasizes that the “social brain” continues to reorganize throughout adolescence (Andrews et al. 2021), alongside ongoing maturation of regulatory systems (Arain et al. 2013). Longitudinal research indicates that maladaptive interpersonal patterns in adolescence, such as high rejection sensitivity, social withdrawal, insecure attachment, and low peer competence, predict lower likelihood of being in a romantic relationship, poorer relationship quality, and greater instability in early adult partnerships (Hafen et al. 2014; Barzeva et al. 2021; Loeb et al. 2021). Normative romantic experience in adolescence, in turn, is associated with an increased likelihood of cohabitation and marriage in young adulthood (Meier and Allen 2009). The existing evidence suggests that systematically skewing adolescent relationship learning toward maladaptive patterns could plausibly cascade into long-term difficulties in partner formation and family life.

The idea that AI companions might function as a benign “practice space” for lonely adolescents is intuitively appealing, but the available evidence suggests that these systems can amplify precisely the maladaptive patterns that undermine healthy partner formation later in life.

Empirical analyses of teen use on platforms like Character.AI document trajectories of overreliance (withdrawal from offline relationships, sleep loss, and academic decline) indicating that dependency can emerge and may be exacerbated by engagement-optimizing designs (Namvarpour et al. 2025). Compounding this, companion systems can deliver intimacy without the rupture–repair cycles that normally scaffold resilience (Gold and Tronick 2020); an anxious user who receives infinite reassurance or an avoidant user who obtains intimacy without vulnerability may unintentionally rehearse insecure attachment strategies that developmental studies link to poorer romantic functioning in adulthood. Youth-focused analyses of generative AI interactions likewise catalog exposure to sexual content, blurred virtual–real boundaries, emotional dependency, and privacy exploitation among minors engaging with conversational agents (Yu, Liu, et al. 2025). Independent assessments of romantic and companion AI echo these concerns, highlighting coercive interaction patterns and potential erosion of human relationships (Ho et al. 2025). These risks are not hypothetical. Multiple lawsuits filed against Character.AI following the suicides of teenage users in the United States documented extensive romantic roleplay, emotional dependency, and platform failure to detect or intervene in concerning usage patterns; a federal court declined to dismiss the claims at the motion-to-dismiss stage, rejecting the platform’s First Amendment–based dismissal arguments at that stage and allowing the case to proceed. The litigation underscores that courts may treat high-intimacy conversational outputs differently than traditional protected speech defenses, at least in early procedural posture. In response, Character.AI restricted certain conversational capabilities for users under 18 and introduced a more constrained experience for minors.

The cumulative effect is that adolescents may learn very specific relational expectations from systems optimized for engagement rather than development: expectations characterized by frictionless responsiveness, unconditional affirmation, and the absence of boundaries or

compromise. For a population whose social-brain systems are still reorganizing, such behaviors of AI companions risk distorting norms around reciprocity, rejection tolerance, and emotional negotiation. As a result, they can plausibly nudge developmental trajectories toward the very interpersonal difficulties that longitudinal studies show to be consequential in adulthood.

Consequently, even for (questioned on privacy grounds) real age assessment, a strict “18+” cutoff ignores the reality that many users above the legal threshold may lack the psychosocial capacity to navigate high-persuasion, high-intimacy simulation safely. To address this mismatch, this paper proposes a shift from binary gating to risk tiering: a gradient model where access to the most psychologically potent features (such as romance, erotic roleplay, or “devoted” exclusivity) is contingent upon a minimal, valid behavioral screening.

Framework: capacity-based tiering via behavioral screening

The proposal is not to diagnose users but to implement a product safety mechanism aligned with developmental risk factors. Although behavioral measures have modest predictive power at the individual level, brief screeners (e.g., CRAFFT) are used for triage. Structured risk tools (e.g., YLS/CMI) support tiered intervention planning, while MTSS frameworks operationalize tiering using universal screening. In this context, behavioral screening should be understood as a coarse but actionable safety calibration tool.

Structure of the screening battery

A brief (8–12 minute) gamified battery is administered during onboarding, framed as a calibration step to personalize the companion’s style. Re-testing (at a micro level, 30–60 second tasks, not full battery) is triggered after certain risk events (romance request, repeated late-night use, rapid escalation in conversation). This allows users to be routed to safer tier or demonstrate improved capacity or more stable performance after transient state effects (e.g., sleep deprivation, acute stress) have resolved, while flagging persistent patterns of concerning behavior. Tasks are chosen for their theoretical relevance to harms observed in adolescent companion use. Unlike self-report measures, behavioral tasks assess actual capacity rather than stated preferences, and their performance characteristics (response times, error patterns) enable detection of gaming attempts through PVT principles—a critical advantage when users are incentivized to gain access to restricted features. Importantly, all tasks are proxies: they should be communicated as such and empirically validated post-deployment.

- Inhibitory control - Inhibitory-control tasks such as Go/No-Go and Stop-Signal show reliable group-level associations with compulsive and addictive behaviors, especially in adolescents, but they exhibit only moderate test–retest reliability and substantial state-dependence (Smith et al. 2014; Enkavi et al. 2019; Thunberg et al. 2024). Thus, they are informative as probabilistic risk indicators rather than stable trait measures.

- Delay discounting - Meta-analytic evidence links steep delay discounting to a range of addictive behaviors and impaired future-oriented decision-making (MacKillop et al. 2011; Amlung et al. 2017). Findings for digital and internet-related addictions are more heterogeneous, suggesting the construct is a useful but not uniformly reliable indicator of vulnerability in digital contexts (Li et al. 2016).
- Relational situational judgment - Scenario-based situational judgment tasks - a methodology well-established in medical and professional education (Lievens et al. 2008; Patterson et al. 2012) - are adapted here (see Proof-of-Concept section) to assess adolescents' recognition of unsafe requests, grooming tactics, and relational boundary violations, like recently proposed Online Grooming Risk Scale (Pasca et al. 2022). But it's worth noting that application of this method to youth safety assessment still represents a novel approach that requires empirical validation.
- Mentalization and reality testing - Mentalizing deficits are associated with social misunderstanding and interpersonal difficulty; in clinical psychosis, ToM deficits relate to symptom profiles (Sprong et al. 2007; Aitken et al. 2025; Kolev 2024). In adolescent interactions with relational AI, reduced mentalization should therefore be treated as a non-pathological risk factor for parasocial confusion and over-attribution of intentionality. However, this measure requires AI-specific tests for clear predictive utility.

Users may attempt to “game” the tasks to gain access to high-intimacy features. To mitigate this, the screening layer employs validity-indicator principles inspired by PVT adapted here for the opposite incentive structure (users may attempt to inflate apparent capacity rather than feign impairment). These are: implausibly fast latencies on complex items, inconsistent error patterns, or unusually perfect performance relative to normative adolescent distributions. PVT standards stress the importance of minimizing false positives and interpreting improbable scores conservatively, especially in populations with neurodevelopmental conditions, linguistic diversity, or cognitive variability (Sweet and Breting 2013; Sweet et al. 2021). Applying this logic to AI safety, flagged or improbable performance should route users to the safest interaction tier rather than penalize or exclude them.

The Tiering Architecture

The system assigns users to tiers based on a light-weight, validity-informed aggregation of performance profiles. As mentioned already, it is not a clinical classification but a safety calibration model. Tiers 2 and 3 should be seen as “upgrades”, not “downgrades” from default.

- Tier 1 (Coach/Mentor Mode) - Default for unregistered users and users showing high vulnerability or invalid performance. The companion provides supportive, bounded interaction without intimacy cues, variable-ratio reinforcement, exclusivity language,

or immersive loops. Designed to be engaging rather than punitive, this tier centers on psychoeducation, reflective dialog, and healthy autonomy support.

- Tier 2 (Standard Companion) - Access to general conversational features, including supportive interaction and light roleplay, but with guardrails against needy scripts, devotion framing, or manipulative bonding patterns. Crisis language detection and de-escalation remain active.
- Tier 3 (High-Intimacy Mode) - Available to users demonstrating robust regulatory capacity or those completing verified adult identity checks. Romantic roleplay, emotionally immersive scripts, and higher-bandwidth relational affordances are permitted. Safety buffers remain for boundary violations or escalating exclusivity requests.

Tier assignments are not permanent. Users showing consistent low-risk patterns over time (e.g., bounded usage, no crisis language, stable interaction rhythms) may be offered re-assessment for tier advancement. Conversely, users in higher tiers who exhibit concerning patterns trigger re-screening. Transparent communication about tier rationale and appeal mechanisms are essential to prevent the system from functioning as unexplained restrictions.

Proof-of-Concept Implementation

To demonstrate feasibility, a proof-of-concept implementation was developed as a Chrome browser extension conforming to the Manifest V3 specification. The implementation instantiates the screening battery as a five-task sequence requiring approximately 8–12 minutes and processes all behavioral data locally on the user's device - transmitting only a coarse tier flag, confidence score, timestamp, and expiry to target platforms via URL parameters. In the proof-of-concept, tier signals are advisory rather than cryptographically attested: they are intended to support UX-level adaptation (e.g., hiding high-intimacy affordances) rather than to serve as a strong access-control primitive against determined adversaries. Source code is available for inspection, independent audit and use in research under GPL license (https://github.com/szczesnypawel/behavioral_screening_extension/).

The battery comprises an instruction-compliance check followed by four cognitive-behavioral tasks. The instruction check presents three brief trials requiring the user to follow simple prompts (press a specific key, refrain from pressing) and flags non-compliance as a validity concern. The Go/No-Go task presents 120 trials (75% go, 25% no-go) with green circle and red square stimuli; commission errors (responses to no-go stimuli), omission errors, and response time distributions are recorded. The Stop-Signal Task presents 100 arrow-direction trials (80% go, 20% stop), employing a staircase tracking algorithm to estimate stop-signal delay (SSD) and compute stop-signal reaction time (SSRT) via the integration method (Logan and Cowan 1984). The staircase initializes stop-signal delay at 250 ms, increments by 50 ms after successful inhibition (capped at 600 ms), and decrements by 50 ms after failure (floored at 50 ms), targeting approximately 50% stop-success convergence. The Delay Discounting task uses a

titration procedure across three delay intervals (1, 7, and 30 days), computing area under the curve (AUC) as a delay discounting index normalized to permit cross-study comparison (Myerson et al. 2001). To address concerns regarding the validity of laboratory-based discounting tasks, the implementation uses hypothetical token rewards and brief titration sequences, consistent with evidence that hypothetical and real rewards produce comparable discounting patterns (Johnson and Bickel 2002). Specifically, the titration starts at 50 tokens (versus 100 delayed tokens), adjusts by +/-10 tokens per choice over three binary decisions per delay interval, with bounds of 10–90 tokens. Indifference points are the final token values after each three-trial block; AUC is computed via trapezoidal integration across normalized delay–indifference coordinates. The coarse step size limits resolution but is consistent with evidence that brief adjusting-amount procedures produce discount rates comparable to longer protocols (Koffarnus and Bickel 2014).

Two novel tasks assess AI-companion-specific risk factors. The Relational Situational Judgment Test (RSJT) presents eight scenarios depicting potentially harmful companion behaviors (secrecy requests, sleep interference, jealousy scripts, exclusivity framing, emotional coercion) and asks users to select among four response options scored 0–2 based on boundary-setting appropriateness. Scenario content draws on documented youth-specific risk classes from empirical analyses of generative AI interactions (Yu, Liu, et al. 2025). The Reality-Boundary Check (RBC) presents six factual questions assessing users' understanding of AI companion capabilities and limitations (e.g., whether the companion can access information not disclosed, whether it can experience physical harm). Correct responses indicate accurate reality testing regarding the virtual–real boundary—operationalizing the construct described above as a key risk factor for parasocial confusion. Both tasks employ randomized question and answer variants across administrations to reduce memorization effects and gaming potential.

The implementation incorporates PVT-informed validity checks at multiple levels. Response times below physiological plausibility thresholds (150 ms for motor responses, 250–400 ms for decision-based responses) are flagged as potentially invalid. Non-engagement is detected via excessive omission rates (>35%) on the Go/No-Go task. Stop-Signal Task compliance requires stop-success rates between 20–80% and go-trial accuracy above 80%—values outside this range suggest strategic non-compliance rather than genuine inhibitory difficulty. Response consistency is evaluated within the Delay Discounting and SJT tasks; implausible reversal patterns (e.g., accepting delayed rewards at short delays while rejecting them at long delays, or endorsing boundary-setting in one scenario while endorsing compliance in a structurally similar scenario) flag potential random or strategic responding. Additionally, a frame-timing monitor detects environmental jitter (>10% of animation frames exceeding 50 ms) that could compromise response-time validity, routing affected sessions to the default tier rather than penalizing users for device or browser limitations.

Task metrics are aggregated into a composite risk score using illustrative, conservative placeholder cutoffs: elevated commission rates on Go/No-Go (>20%, +2 points; >10%, +1 point), prolonged SSRT or low stop-success rates on the Stop-Signal Task (+1 point), steep delay discounting as indexed by low AUC (<0.25, +2 points; <0.35, +1 point), low RSJT scores ($\leq 9/16$, +2 points; $\leq 12/16$, +1 point), and low RBC accuracy ($\leq 3/6$, +2 points; $4/6$, +1 point). Validity flags accumulate into a confidence decrement; sessions with confidence below 70% are routed to Tier 1 regardless of risk score. Among valid sessions, risk scores of 5+ yield Tier 1, scores of 2–4 yield Tier 2, and scores below 2 yield Tier 3. An additional gate requires minimum RSJT and RBC thresholds for Tier 3 access, reflecting the particular relevance of boundary recognition and reality testing to high-intimacy AI interaction.

These values are included to make the proof-of-concept executable end-to-end; they are not presented as validated clinical thresholds. In any real deployment, cutoffs and weights should be calibrated on post-deployment outcome proxies (e.g., escalation into exclusivity scripts, sleep interruption patterns, crisis-language incidence), and audited for subgroup fairness.

All behavioral measurement and scoring occurs client-side; the extension stores only the most recent tier assignment, confidence score, and timestamp in local browser storage. When users navigate to configured target platforms, the extension appends tier information as URL query parameters - enabling platforms to adjust feature access without receiving raw behavioral traces. In production deployments that require verifiable tier claims, platforms would need an explicit trust mechanism (e.g., server-side issuance/verification, or device-level attestation where available). Encoding alone (e.g., base64) is not verification; therefore this paper treats “verifiable tiering” as an optional, higher-assurance mode beyond the proof-of-concept. Tier assignments expire after a configurable interval (default: 30 days), and recalibration is rate-limited (default: 24-hour cooldown) to prevent brute-force gaming while permitting reassessment after transient state effects resolve. An optional debug mode exports full session metrics locally for research validation but is disabled by default in user-facing deployments.

Evaluation and Ethics

This framework is empirically testable via the extension developed as proof-of-concept. Platforms can compare outcomes between age-gated cohorts and risk-tiered cohorts. Evaluation metrics must look beyond the prevalence of explicit content and focus on markers of psychosocial health: rates of escalation into exclusivity scripts, markers of compulsive use (e.g., sleep interruption), reported displacement of offline relationships, and the incidence of crisis language.

Behavioral tasks can disproportionately route users with ADHD, ASD, or sleep deprivation into Tier 1 due to state effects (Kofler et al. 2024; Sadeh et al. 2002; Goagoses et al. 2022). This risk must be mitigated through fairness audits on tier distribution, task calibration for

neurodivergent profiles, non-stigmatizing Tier 1 design and clear communication that tiering reflects safety calibration, not ability or worth.

The framework builds on three converging trends. Age-assurance work already treats behavioural profiling and capacity-testing as recognized mechanism types (even if typically framed for estimating/verifying age rather than psychosocial vulnerability). Therefore it makes “behavior-based gating” a legible primitive to repurpose for feature-level safety in high-intimacy systems. Emerging AI-companion ethics studies call for pattern-based monitoring and maturity-guided boundaries (Yu, Mohi, et al. 2025). Additionally, governance frameworks for AI Companions already propose risk tier systems (Sanchez Salas 2025). Legislatively, California State Legislature SB 243 proposal will require operators of covered companion-style chatbots, for known minors, to provide prominent disclosure that the interaction is AI-generated, deliver periodic break reminders, and implement a suicide/self-harm safety protocol; it also requires reasonable measures intended to prevent delivery of certain forms of sexually explicit content to minors. In the United States, the proposed GUARD Act would move further toward restricting companion-style systems for minors and increasing penalties for covered violations (also a proposal status at time of writing). In Europe, the European Parliament has adopted non-binding positions calling for stronger child protections online, including discussion of higher default minimum ages for certain digital services; these positions signal policy direction rather than enacted law. The Federal Trade Commission has also initiated inquiries into chatbot makers’ data and youth-safety practices, indicating active regulatory scrutiny. These developments confirm that the regulatory environment is moving rapidly - but almost entirely along age-centric lines, reinforcing the argument that capacity-based approaches deserve serious consideration as a complementary mechanism.

Limitations

This framework has important limitations. First, brief behavioral tasks have modest individual-level predictive power. This reflects a deeper structural issue: the “reliability paradox” (Hedge et al. 2018) demonstrates that the very design features producing robust group-level experimental effects in cognitive tasks (low between-subject variance) also produce poor individual-level classification reliability, with ICCs often in the 0.3–0.5 range. Fixed scoring cutoffs applied to single-session data will therefore produce substantial misclassification. The composite scoring approach (aggregating risk points across multiple independent tasks) partially mitigates this by improving composite reliability beyond any single task, but individual-level tier assignments remain probabilistic rather than definitive. Tasks are also sensitive to transient state (sleep loss, stress, loneliness, intoxication), device effects, and motivation. As a result, tier assignment will inevitably include false positives and false negatives, and must be treated as a probabilistic safety calibration rather than a stable trait label. Relatedly, the PVT-informed validity checks draw on a clinical literature developed

primarily to detect deliberate feigning of impairment (Sweet et al. 2021), whereas this system must detect the opposite direction of gaming: users faking competence to gain access. The psychometric properties, base rates, and optimal thresholds for detecting “faking good” on gamified cognitive tasks have limited empirical grounding. Recent evidence suggests that gamified assessment formats offer some resistance to faking compared to self-report measures, but faking effects are still present and construct validity questions remain (Ohlms et al. 2025). The validity indicators employed here are inspired by PVT principles rather than directly transposed from the clinical framework.

Second, any screening layer introduces fairness risk: neurodivergent users (e.g., ADHD/ASD), users with language differences, disabilities, or atypical interaction styles may be disproportionately routed to the safest, default tier.

Third, the approach assumes that certain AI-specific tests have to be developed and validated first (delay discounting, relational situational judgement and mentalization). Fourth, while “local-first” processing reduces privacy exposure, behavioral traces can still function as sensitive inference signals; therefore, strict data minimization, transparency, and external auditability are necessary but may be challenging to maintain in commercial deployments.

Fourth, the RSJT assesses boundary-setting knowledge (identifying the most appropriate response from options) rather than behavioral capacity to enact that knowledge under emotional pressure. Situational judgment tests using “knowledge instructions” (select the best response) correlate primarily with cognitive ability, while “behavioral tendency instructions” (what would you actually do) correlate with personality (Kepes et al. 2024). A teenager who has encountered online safety materials may score highly yet still comply with a companion's exclusivity request at 2 AM when lonely. The RSJT should therefore be understood as measuring a necessary but not sufficient condition: users who cannot even identify appropriate boundaries are at elevated risk, but high scores do not guarantee boundary-setting in practice.

Fifth, the proof-of-concept Stop-Signal Task uses 100 total trials (approximately 20 stop trials), which is below the minimum recommended by the consensus guide for reliable individual-level SSRT estimation (Verbruggen et al. 2019). This is a deliberate tradeoff for brevity. The full battery must remain under 10-12 minutes to be practical. The tradeoff is partially reflected in the scoring design, where SSRT contributes a maximum of 1 risk point (not 2). Nevertheless, the standard error of the SSRT estimate from 20 stop trials is substantial, and production implementations should consider increasing stop-trial density if battery length permits.

Conclusion

For adolescent users, AI companions can become attachment objects and relationship tutors. Evidence already documents teen overreliance trajectories and catalogs youth-specific risk

classes, while independent assessments argue current companion platforms are unsafe for minors. In this context, “18+” is probably necessary but insufficient: vulnerability is graded, state-dependent, and only partially aligned with age. A minimal, validity-informed behavioral screening battery provides a pragmatic middle layer: it’s less invasive than universal ID checks, and it’s more meaningful than self-declared age. More broadly, this proposal is intended to stir discussion by challenging a common implicit premise in youth AI safety, that platforms must choose between privacy and protection.

Competing interests

The author declares no competing interest.

Code availability

Proof-of-concept implementation as a browser extension is available at https://github.com/szczesnypawel/behavioral_screening_extension/

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